

1 **HIV-2 infection in PBMC.**

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7 HIV-2 infection mechanics are likely significantly different than those of HIV-1. We measured total gene
8 expression in the peripheral blood in humans with HIV-2 infection and compared it to that of healthy
9 individuals or individuals with HIV-1 infection. We demonstrate here selective activation of *Iff6* in humans
10 with HIV-2 infection. In HIV-2 but not in HIV-1, we observed selective up-regulation of the chemokine
11 *Ccl15*. Cellular machinery functioning in host defense was also different in HIV-2 infection. We describe
12 here specific induction of *Wdr54* in HIV-2 infection.

13 Citations

14 1. Gottlieb, G.S., Hawes, S.E., Kiviat, N.B. and Sow, P.S., 2008. Differences in proviral DNA load
15 between HIV-1-infected and HIV-2-infected patients. *Aids*, 22(11), pp.1379-1380.

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